

Genome assembly, annotation, and comparative genomic analyses of *Rhizobium leguminosarum* bv. *viciae* strain D70

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Abstract

We report the draft genome sequence of *Rhizobium leguminosarum* biovar *viciae* strain D70, an agricultural microorganism isolated from pea nodules and associated with biological nitrogen fixation as the reference inoculant strain for pea, vetch, and lentil production in Argentina. Genome sequencing and comparative genomic analyses revealed genes and/or biosynthetic clusters potentially related to symbiosis, nutrient acquisition, and specialized metabolites involved in environmental adaptation. Notably, its remarkably large genome size (7.73 Mbp) and the presence of uncharacterized biosynthetic clusters underscore its high metabolic versatility. The assembled genome comprises 7,730,457 bp distributed in 169 contigs with a GC content of 60.57%.

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In Argentina, *Rhizobium leguminosarum* bv. *viciae* strain D70 is widely used in commercial inoculants for vetch, field pea, and lentil and is endorsed by the National Agricultural Technology Institute (INTA, Argentina) for its ability to establish early nodulation and effectively fix nitrogen across diverse cultivars and environments. The D70 strain is deposited in the LBPCV-IMYZA INTA collection (WDCM 31) and was originally isolated from vetch (*Vicia benghalensis*) nodules in Chachapoyas, Salta Province, Argentina, in 1959 (Piccinetti et al., 2024). Consistent with its classification as *R. leguminosarum* bv. *viciae*, strain D70 effectively nodulates members of the pea–vetch symbiotic group, including pea, vetch, lentil, *Lathyrus* spp., and faba bean. Field studies have demonstrated high and stable biological nitrogen fixation performance. For example, Enrico et al. (2020) reported an average biological nitrogen fixation (BNF) contribution of 99 kg N ha⁻¹ and a BNF efficiency of 60% in vetch, whereas Piccinetti et al. (2024) reported a BNF contribution of 132 kg N ha⁻¹ and a BNF efficiency of 72% in field pea across multiple environments in the Pampas region. Moreover, residual nitrogen derived from D70-inoculated vetch provided benefits to maize comparable to those achieved with synthetic nitrogen fertilization, highlighting its contribution to the sustainability of soybean–maize production systems (Gudelj et al., 2010; Enrico et al., 2020).

Despite its extensive use, the genomic basis of strain D70 for symbiotic efficiency, adaptability, and contribution to nitrogen cycling remained unexplored. Understanding its genetic makeup is essential for optimizing its use as a bioinoculant and enhancing its performance under varying environmental conditions. This study presents the draft genome of *R. leguminosarum* bv. *viciae* strain D70, offering the first insights into its genetic basis for effective nitrogen fixation and nodulation.

Genomic DNA was extracted using the Wizard Genomic DNA Purification Kit (Promega). Paired-end libraries (2 × 150 bp) were prepared and sequenced on an Illumina platform at ANLIS “Dr. Carlos G. Malbrán” (Buenos Aires, Argentina). Reads were de novo assembled with SPAdes (Bankevich et al., 2012) through the KBase platform (Arkin et al., 2018). Genome completeness and contamination were assessed using CheckM (Parks et al., 2015). Species delineation was carried out using the TYGS pipeline and pubMLST (Meier-Kolthoff & Göker, 2019). For phylogenetic analysis, digital DNA–DNA hybridization (dDDH) values were calculated using TYGS (Meier-Kolthoff & Göker, 2019), and Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) analyses were performed using JSpeciesWS (Richter et al., 2016). Genome annotation was performed using RASTtk (Aziz et al., 2008; Brettin et al., 2015). Biosynthetic gene clusters were predicted using antiSMASH (Blin et al., 2019).

Assembly statistics are summarized in Table 1. The genome assembly showed high completeness and negligible contamination, indicating that it provides a reliable representation of the genetic repertoire of strain D70. The overall genome size falls within the range reported for members of *R. leguminosarum*, reflecting the relatively large and versatile genomes characteristic of this species and its adaptation to diverse soil and rhizosphere environments (Young et al., 2006; Afonin et al., 2020). Likewise, the GC content and coding capacity are consistent with those described for other strains of the species, supporting both the taxonomic assignment and the integrity of the assembly. Although the assembly remains fragmented, this is expected for a draft genome generated exclusively from short-read Illumina sequencing data, particularly in rhizobial genomes that often harbor repetitive sequences and multiple replicons (Young et al., 2006). Nevertheless, the contiguity metrics indicate that a substantial fraction of the genome is contained within relatively large contigs, enabling robust gene prediction, functional annotation, and comparative genomic analyses.

Table 1. Assembly statistics for *Rhizobium leguminosarum* bv. *viciae* strain D70.

Feature	Value
Genome size (bp)	7,730,457
Number of contigs	169
Largest contig (bp)	837,969
GC content (%)	60.57
N50 (bp)	164,226
L50	12

Genome completeness (%)	99.71
Genome contamination (%)	0.14
Protein-coding sequences (CDSs)	8,028

Genome-based taxonomic analyses placed strain D70 within *R. leguminosarum*. Initial taxonomic assignment using TYGS and PubMLST identified strain D70 as *R. leguminosarum* with 100% confidence based on comparisons with reference genomes. Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) analyses performed using JSpecies yielded values of 99.4% (ANiB) and 99.8% (ANIm), while digital DNA–DNA hybridization (dDDH) analysis using TYGS showed 98.6% similarity relative to *R. leguminosarum* strain DSM 106839, confirming its placement within this species.

Genome annotation revealed a comprehensive repertoire of genes associated with biological nitrogen fixation, symbiosis, nutrient acquisition, and environmental adaptation. Genes encoding the structural components of the Mo-Fe nitrogenase (*nifH*, *nifD*, and *nifK*), proteins involved in FeMo-cofactor biosynthesis and maturation (*nifB*, *nifE*, *nifN*, and *nifU*), the transcriptional activator *nifA*, and the fixABCX electron transfer complex were identified, indicating the presence of the core genetic machinery required for nitrogen fixation (Dixon & Kahn, 2004). Additional components involved in the regulation and functioning of nitrogen fixation, including the oxygen-responsive *fixLJ* two-component regulatory system, as well as key nitrogen regulatory genes (*rpoN*, *ntrB*, *ntrC*, and *glnK*), were also detected (Dixon & Kahn, 2004). The genome further harbors functions related to ammonia assimilation, including glutamine synthetase (*glnA*), glutamate synthase, ammonium transporters, and nitrogen regulatory proteins, supporting the assimilation of fixed nitrogen into cellular metabolism.

In addition, a complete set of major nodulation determinants (*nodD*, *nodA*, *nodB*, *nodC*, *nodL*, and *nodX*) was identified, consistent with the ability of strain D70 to establish effective symbiotic interactions with leguminous hosts. Genes associated with rhizosphere colonization, including exopolysaccharide biosynthesis and modification proteins (*exoF*, *exoQ*, and *exoZ*), were also detected, supporting traits related to root attachment, biofilm formation, and infection thread development. Furthermore, the genome contains multiple genes involved in osmotic stress adaptation, including trehalose biosynthesis (*otsA*, *otsB*, and *treS*), glycine-betaine uptake and metabolism (*proXVW* and *gbcA*), and choline transport (*choXVW*), suggesting an enhanced capacity to persist under fluctuating soil environmental conditions. Additional genes potentially associated with phosphate solubilization, including a PQQ-dependent glucose dehydrogenase (*gcd*) and a quinoprotein oxidoreductase, were also identified. Genome annotation further revealed limited but notable evidence of genes potentially associated with auxin metabolism, including an indole-3-acetic acid acetyltransferase, multiple nitrilases, and auxin-related transport proteins. However, canonical markers of the major bacterial indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) biosynthetic pathways (*ipdC*, *iaaM*, and *iaaH*) were not detected, preventing definitive inference of auxin production from genomic data alone. Together, these features reflect the genetic potential of strain D70 to establish effective symbioses and to persist

and compete in rhizosphere environments under variable environmental conditions (Young et al., 2006).

AntiSMASH analysis revealed 13 putative biosynthetic gene clusters associated with the production of specialized metabolites involved in environmental adaptation and plant-associated lifestyles. Among them, a siderophore biosynthetic cluster showed high similarity to the vicibactin pathway (Dilworth et al., 1998), which may enhance iron acquisition and competitiveness in the rhizosphere. This finding complements the genomic evidence of rhizosphere adaptation identified through the presence of exopolysaccharide biosynthesis genes and multiple osmoprotection systems. Additional clusters related to homoserine lactone-mediated quorum sensing, ectoine biosynthesis, and arylpolyene production were also identified (Calatrava-Morales et al., 2018; Czech et al., 2018; Schöner et al., 2016), suggesting mechanisms associated with microbial communication, stress tolerance, and environmental persistence. Notably, several predicted clusters exhibited low similarity to previously characterized biosynthetic pathways, highlighting an unexplored metabolic potential for novel specialized metabolite discovery in strain D70. Although classical siderophore biosynthetic markers were not identified during the targeted PGPR gene survey, the detection of a vicibactin-like biosynthetic cluster suggests the presence of an alternative iron acquisition strategy commonly found in rhizobia.

The genomic information generated for strain D70 advances the characterization of a key agricultural microorganism in Argentina, offering crucial insights into its proven efficiency as a reference bioinput for regional crop management. Collectively, the genomic profile of D70 is consistent with that of a highly specialized symbiotic rhizobium whose agronomic performance relies primarily on efficient nodulation, biological nitrogen fixation, rhizosphere colonization, and environmental persistence, with additional genomic evidence suggesting a limited contribution of other plant growth-promoting traits.

Data Availability

This Whole Genome Shotgun project has been deposited at GenBank under the accession number JBZEGZ000000000.

BioProject: PRJNA1476340

BioSample: SAMN60709954

Additional bioinformatic outputs, genome annotation files, and supplementary sequence data generated during this study are available in a companion dataset associated with this genome report.

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Keywords

Agricultural microbiology; microbial genomics; comparative genomics; microbial bioinputs; PGPR; nitrogen fixation; agricultural biotechnology

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